

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Mironowicz****FIRST NAME: Elzbieta****PROGRAM CODE: MIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr Gulma**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.
The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical) and WHO style
The author did use Zotero to insert references
The author did use Grammarly Edu
The author used the following software: MS Office Professional Plus 2019 on Windows 10

Seven critical concepts with the page number in-text:

1. Introduction (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 1)
2. New fantastic tools (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 2)
3. The fall of the Wikipedia (Cleenewerck and Gulma, 2021 3)
4. Paraphrases and plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 3)
5. Form and style issue (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 3)
6. Logical flow (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 4)
7. Conclusion (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 4)

MY FIRST RESPONSE PAPER AT EUCLID UNIVERSITY

1) INTRODUCTION

Restarting the university at the turn of fifty is a big challenge. Only to find a suitable master's course was a long journey for me which lasted almost ten months. Finally, happy to become a student of Euclid University, a unique institution that will give me tools to become a world-class professional, I started to study for the first period at the ACA-401 course.

The first period is about professional writing, the ability I need in my future job, nevertheless complicated in my situation. Thirty years ago, I arrived in Italy, speaking now fluently Italian but still having difficulties in formal writing. Additionally, without practice, I am not any more fluent in my mother tongue Polish. Imagine now writing an academic essay in English. Moreover, my professional writing has been bound up to now to hand over nursing reports, daily email communications and short articles published on the intranet or newspaper at my workplace. However, I will transform my initial confusion into something which will give me future satisfaction. I have to believe in myself and conscientiously follow my instructors' explanations to be successful. I confirm by quoting

Colin Powell, that: "A dream does not become a reality through magic; it takes sweat, determination, and hard work" (OSMQuote 2019).

This paper will design my path to a greater understanding of the Response Paper (RP) rules.

2) NEW FANTASTIC TOOLS

When I opened the study material on LMS (Learning Management System) on the Euclid University website, I gradually understood that it would not be easy and require plenty of time to write an academic essay based on international academic rules. However, the use of new excellent tools as Grammarly and Zotero will make it easier.

a) Grammarly

I have never heard before about Grammarly, a fantastic tool. Previously, I needed to ask for text corrections from some of my native English-speaking friends. The arrival of Grammarly was revolutionary for me, and I can check my writing independently! Grammarly corrects grammar and sentence structure, word choice, punctuation, capitalization, and spelling (Sebranek, Kemper, and Meyer 1999, 82–83). I appreciate the suggestions by Roshan in the Grammarly Tutorial video to copy and paste the text directly in Grammarly. In that way, more feedback is possible, and the plagiarism rate is calculated (Roshan 2018).

Moreover, a wide selection of synonyms is available on Grammarly. As I could not find Grammarly Premium on my account, I asked the online Grammarly Support explanations; as a result, they confirmed there is no difference between the Premium and @edu accounts. I am thankful to EUCLID the Grammarly will for sure contribute to my success.

b) Zotero

Another fantastic tool, Zotero, is doing "an amazing work when it comes to inserting footnotes or references and also creating and structuring bibliography" (EUCLID 2017). When I graduated from nursing, my research thesis was the best one in 20 classmates. I spent about four months just collecting data, information and sources. I remember that creating a bibliography by myself was a hard job, but I did not know Zotero at the time. I appreciate adding references in multiple ways, such as manually or with an identifier, finally using the Zotero Connector (Top Tip Bio 2021). In conclusion, I enjoy creating collections, even if it took time to understand how to do it properly.

3) THE FALL OF THE WIKIPEDIA

I used to consult Wikipedia on many occasions, whereas Euclid University stays that “Students should never use Wikipedia as a source” (Euclid University 2020, 9). Still, Euclid University recommends other sources such as Questia or JSTOR, the most extensive library of academic journals, to consult as many as possible authors for evidence-based writing.

Wikipedia was my preferred general investigation source until now. Evidence-based medicine on PubMed, CDC (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention), or WHO (World Health Organization) websites inspire my nursing career. My daily job, which bases on medical research, is followed by practical experience on the ground. With great pleasure, I will implement the research ability into my academic writing.

4) PARAPHRASES AND PLAGIARISM

I was also surprised to see that “paraphrasing is plagiarism if credit is not given to the original author” (Sebranek, Kemper, and Meyer 1999, 229). I can find in study material that “A feature of most academic writing is that it draws on the work of other writers and researchers” (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 2). However, “It is not fair to take someone’s work and not give them credit” (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 5). Moreover, plagiarism is penalized in academics; however, avoiding it is possible by introducing quotations, paraphrases and citations. Finally, it is mandatory to indicate the plagiarism rate with Grammarly Premium (Euclid University 2020, 3), and it must be less than 18%. I thought that copying and pasting from acknowledged sources is a typical action commonly used by everybody, and there is nothing wrong with this. But now, I am aware that I must give credit to the authors to rewrite someone's ideas or words.

5) FORM AND STYLE ISSUE

“At EUCLID, the form is extremely important” (Euclid University 2020, 5). It should be easy with the template provided and Turabian Style set up in Microsoft Word. However, as a Public Health student, I will start familiarizing myself with WHO style and British English. It took me some time to understand how to make it work all simultaneously. This paper will introduce some WHO style recommendations, mainly while formatting the bibliography and using an ellipsis in the quotations. Following the WHO style, I would propose “do not abbreviate Professor” (World Health Organization 2013, 19).

The final purpose of applying different styles is to treat text correctly and consistently as it stays at WHO style guide:

"Any professional publisher has a house style: the preferred spelling, punctuation, terminology, and formatting to be used for all its information products in all media. House

style increases WHO's credibility. ... Issuing a range of high-quality products strengthens the WHO brand and its logo as a mark of quality. ... Finally, following house style... increases the efficiency of the writing and editing process" (World Health Organization 2013, 1).

6) LOGICAL FLOW

The first step is gathering information while reading, skimming, and scanning (Sebranek, Kemper, and Meyer 1999, 322). Subsequently, it is necessary to organize findings logically, which will result interesting and easy to follow. The logical flow is much more achievable using conjunctions and transition signals, magical words connecting ideas and adding cohesion to an essay.

7) CONCLUSION

For me, choosing words with feelings is important, or as a guide to writing says, I love compelling stories, authors who write in an honest, sincere and natural style. (Sebranek, Kemper, and Meyer 1999, 134-136). In my daily job, I take part in editing short articles for Health & Wellbeing Program purposes. To raise the readers' acceptance, I try to add words that carry feelings and emotions, not only scientific evidence. The feedback from others confirms that it is vital to find words with the right meaning and feelings while giving information. In my opinion, the academic or professional essay must be convincing and credible; in other words, all is tremendously significant: appearance, content, and emotions.

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